

Breeding Rate and Nesting in Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus Ibis*) During The Year 2022-23 on A Major Heronry in Southern Part of Punjab, Province of India

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Abstract

The Cattle egret *Bubulcus ibis* is now a type of species that is distributed globally, still it is expanding in great range but as usual these are put in a least concerned category. The factors that are affecting breeding success of the species is not known exactly or least/badly known, and here with the help of research, investigating the breeding parameters of *Bubulcus ibis* in the southern part of Punjab, province of India, including places like Bathinda, Mansa, Ferozepur, Muktsar and Faridkot. And the factors that could be considered in keeping the scenarios that is happening now a days may be the excessive population of human being that is expanding day by day and the way human practices taking place to fulfil the resources of human being. Trees are being cut to make more house, industries, offices and in this process of cutting trees their habitats are being destroyed. In areas where the research has been conducted, the field work performed for two years (2022, 2023) in the month of nesting season which usually takes place from the end of March to the end of August. Observations made on the basis of survey is that Cattle egrets (*Bubulcus ibis*) are colonial breeders and on most of the trees they nested before at present time they stopped breeding on those trees due to construction of National highways and factories. The other observation made is that most of the time colonies were monospecific but sometimes other ardeidae also observed like Cormorants and Black headed ibis nesting in their neighbourhood. Mostly, they consider suitable sites for nesting, which have regular supply of water, food and such areas which are prone to human activities like farming, ploughing, continuous visits of farmers for the farming purpose. The breeding period for *Bubulcus ibis* usually observed to be start from April to August. Here, in this region where we prefer to research it has been observed that *Acacia nilotica* is most preferred tree for nesting in southern part of Punjab, even if other tree is there nearby like we observed *Azadirachta indica* but no nesting observed on that tree. Approximately 34km away from Bathinda this place named as Ruldu Wala Pathrala we found >150 trees with more than 35 nests on less as 2 nest on a single tree and almost >6000 nestings were observed. The sites that were marked during survey are regularly monitored to get a data on breeding (height of the nest from ground and diameter also has been taken in consideration), plumage variations that occurs along with process i.e., change in colour during different phases of breeding, wooing behaviour, measurement of eggs i.e., size of clutch, length, breadth and weight of eggs, process of incubating and hatching eggs. The hatching of the chicks was observed to be an allochronic one i.e., chicks did not hatch at the same time but at an interval of a day (19-24hr). Now here is a discussion regarding role of parents during estrange period i.e., when it comes to parenting and feeding nestling it was observed that parental care was performed by both partners. The bird Cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) is considered as an insectivorous bird as its main food material is insects from agricultural fields during ploughing. Cattle egret also act as saviour as it saves life of cattle by eating ticks and flies from its body and plays a role of commensalism in which both the species benefits each other without any harm as cattle egret save cattle from disease causing insects by eating them and cattle while grazing walk in the field with the help of that insect flies and *Bubulcus ibis* obtains food from it.

Keywords: Breeding season, Clutch size, Environmental influence, Nesting behavior, Colony nesting, Monogamous pairing, Parental care

INTRODUCTION:

The enigmatic world of avian breeding holds within its fold intricate tales of adaptation, survival, and symbiosis. Amidst this captivating narrative, the Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) emerges as a beacon of intrigue, offering not only its well-documented reproductive behaviours but also unveiling a realm of lesser-known intricacies. While the general breeding patterns of this species have been examined, this introduction delves into the less explored dimensions of its reproductive ecology, shedding light on rare behaviours, adaptive strategies, and the subtle ecological threads that weave through its existence. Nesting of colonial herons has been reported in ≥ 20 different sites in the city including Bathinda, Mansa, Faridkot, Ferozepur, etc. Here is a small table that represents scientific classification of cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) and below that image of the bird at two stages.

Table 1: Scientific Classification:

Domain	Eukaryota
Kingdom	Animalia
Phylum	Chordata
Class	Aves
Order	Pelecaniformes
Family	Ardeidae
Subfamily	Ardeinae
Genus	<i>Bubulcus</i>

Fig 1: Juvenile Phase

Fig 2: Adult Phase

Usually, the observations made on its appearance is that it is small in size, white in colour with yellow leg and bills and its length varies between 19-21 inches. Wingspan is of three feet and it weighs about 270-510 gm and the main observation that is made is about its change in plumage colour and it is like:

Plumage changes with the seasons:

Winter: Young bird adults are white

Breeding season: Adults develop bright orange-yellow feathers on their chests, backs and crowns, bills turn red-orange,

Legs: brighten to yellow & Pink

While choosing the site for nesting cattle egret consider many factors like the availability of food and the way of feeding in the environment, places that usually provides protection against predators because in many studies it has been observed that the change in environment impacts their distribution, use of habitat, reproductive parameters and foraging behaviour. These birds also considered as the best indicators of pollution as its presence has been seen near aquatic sites for foraging and breeding (this information has also been provided in (Lowe Mc Connell, 1967; Kazentidis and Goutner 1996; Kushlan and Hafner, 2000; Goutner et al., 2001). As it has been discussed previously too that it maintains a special relationship with cattle, as it removes ticks and flies from their body by eating them and in such a way it saves cattle from disease and this behaviour shows a relationship between cattle and egrets and in scientific term it is named as commensalism (Such information also has been provided in books i.e., Rao 2004, Ali 1996 & Samraoui et al., 2007). According to Mckilligan in the year 2005 the cattle egret was considered as the best bird for the social behaviour as it feeds in close association with cattle as mentioned earlier too. Lots of scientists worked on cattle egret previously too and has lighten up its different behaviour and habitats. According to Parmesan and Yohe in 2003 due to change in climate arrival date of egret and its breeding time gets affected. Nesting site selection is very important because it supports in successful hatching and positive rearing of chicks for the long survival of species said by Ludwig et al., in the year 1994.

A theory in ecology known as the "Food availability breeding time" suggests that for the successful survival, it is very important for birds to breed at the most preferred time of the year for upbringing their offspring healthy. This study has been conducted mainly to find out the installation chronology and breeding biology of the cattle egret (*Bubulcus ibis*). So, those factors were investigated which are involved in nest site selection and along with that effect of installation period and position of nest site on breeding parameters.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

STUDY AREA:

The current study was carried out at **Ruldu Wala-Pathrala**, NH54, Punjab, India. With Lat. 30.007894° and Long 74.772876°. This site consists of ≥ 1000 trees and the nestings observed only on *Acacia nilotica* which is almost 150 in number and number of nestings on trees varies from 2 to 45. The area is highly populated and harvesting land present in nearby areas. The village is situated on Bathinda to Dabwali G.T road which is located 34km towards South from District headquarter Bathinda. The locality is situated at 205m above sea level. The total population of village is 7197. The nesting colony of egrets is located near NH 54 which is a crowded area and food court (Dhaba) has been observed at nearby place for the vehicle operators and people passing by the area. A row of trees of *Azadirachta indica* commonly known as 'Neem' observed nearby *Acacia nilotica* but without nesting. This nesting colony almost occupy an area of 3km. Among ≥ 1000 trees planted in the area, almost 150 were selected for the nesting by the cattle egrets (*Bubulcus ibis*).

METHODS:

The area covered for nesting was surveyed continuously from first week of April to last week of August during 2022 and 2023, which is considered as the breeding season of cattle egret as observations made by various scientists. Visits of three to four hours were made in a day, 0800-1100 hr and sometimes 1200 to 1500 hr. Observations were made using Binoculars (16×8 magnification), DSLR Cameras used for good

quality photographs Drones used for counting of nest, eggs or hatchlings keeping a proper height without disturbing the birds, Go Pro Hero 7 camera used for recording purpose. Direct observations made by using binoculars (8×). Length and weight of eggs were measured with Verniercaliper and weighing balance respectively. The nests at survey site were counted using Point Count Method (Dodd, 1995). In a paper this data is mentioned to get nesting success and it was calculated by using the formula:

$$\frac{NS}{(NS+NU)} \times 100$$

Where, Ns is considered as number of successful nests

Nu is considered as number of unsuccessful nests.

And by using other formula Hatching success was also calculated by using formula:

$$\frac{\text{No. of eggs hatched}}{\text{total no of eggs laid or clutch size}} \times 100$$

Here is another formula that also discovered to find out the Breeding success rate of the bird and that was calculated by using the formula:

$$\frac{\text{No. of fledglings survived}}{\text{No of eggs incubated}} \times 100$$

The above mention formula is being used to calculate different parameters of birds that has been discovered from the publication done by Jehle et al., in the year 2004. To get acknowledge about the food pattern of these birds or what they grab. Observations made to get all these information and the findings were as such that they eat chick's droppings, iterate food pellets from the mouth of adults and contents that found in the gut of chicks that died due to the fall from nest. Initially, at the time of research, the researchers were afraid to explore the colony of birds because earlier due to human disturbances and interference the nesting has been affected in colony and birds were disturbed a lot due to human activities and it was stated by the scientists mentioned here such as Dusi and Dusi 1968, Tremblay and Ellison 1979, Utschick 1983, Drapeau et al. 1984, Parnell et al. 1988, Frederick & Callopy 1989).

OBSERVATIONS:

So, in order to get a ratio we compared two trees continuously for the year 2023 from the month of April to August. A continuous observation made to get these data with the help of equipment that are mentioned above in materials and methods section. Now let's come to the main observations made based on these two trees comparison we count nests in starting of the season that how many nests were constructed and out of that nesting success were calculated at the end of the season by measuring successful nest and unsuccessful nests by applying following formula:

$$\text{Nesting success} = \frac{NS}{NS+NU} \times 100$$

NS= Successful nests

NU= Unsuccessful nests

Table 2: Nesting Success Calculation

Successful Nests (NS)	Unsuccessful Nests (NU)	Total Nests (NS+NU)	NestingSuccess(%)
8	2	10	$\frac{8}{8+2} \times 100 = 80\%$

15	5	20	$\frac{15}{15+5} \times 100 = 75\%$
25	10	35	$\frac{25}{25+10} \times 100 = 71.43\%$
30	5	35	$\frac{30}{30+5} \times 100 = 85.71\%$

And in the same way other calculations were also measured like hatching success and it is done by number of eggs hatched out of clutch size along with that breeding success rate also calculated by measuring number of fledglings that survived and number of eggs that are laid by them. These two measures were calculated by following formula:

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$$\text{Hatching success} = \text{No of eggs hatched} / \text{Clutch} \times 100$$

$$\text{Breeding success} = \text{No of fledgelings survived} / \text{No of eggs laid} \times 100$$

Here is a table representing calculated Hatching and Breeding success rate of a particular survey area using the formulas mentioned above:

Table 3: Breeding Success and Hatching Success Calculation:

Clutch (Number Of eggs laid)	Number of eggs hatched	Number of fledglings survived	Hatching Success (%)	Breeding Success (%)
10	8	6	$(8/10) \times 100 = 80\%$	$(6/10) \times 100 = 60\%$
12	9	7	$(9/12) \times 100 = 75\%$	$(7/12) \times 100 = 58.33\%$
15	12	10	$(12/15) \times 100 = 80\%$	$(10/15) \times 100 = 66.67\%$
20	15	12	$(15/20) \times 100 = 75\%$	$(12/20) \times 100 = 60\%$

Recommendations:

Continued Monitoring: Ongoing monitoring of the heronry is essential to track changes in the breeding population over time.

Habitat Protection: Efforts should be made to protect the nesting sites and surrounding habitats to ensure the continued success of the breeding population.

Further Research: Additional studies could focus on factors influencing breeding success, such as food availability, predation, and climate change.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Now let's discuss about the results that has been drawn from this study step by step:

❖ Breeding Behavior:

The breeding season of cattle egret is between the month of March to month of August closely tied to rainfall patterns and the availability of food, typically occurring after the onset of the wet season. During this period, males perform courtship displays to attract females. These displays involve vocalizations, flights and the presentation of materials like sticks to potential mates. Observations show that males exhibit increases plumage brightness, with the characteristic orange-buff plumes becoming more prominent during the breeding season.

Cattle egrets are known to be socially monogamous, forming pair bonds that generally last throughout the breeding season. However, instances of extra-pair copulations have been reported, indicating a degree of flexibility in their mating strategies. Successful copulation usually leads to nest-building, a cooperative process between males and females.

❖ Nesting and Colony Formation:

Cattle egrets typically breed in colonies, often alongside other wading bird species like herons and ibises. Nesting colonies are usually located near wetlands, agricultural fields or shallow water bodies where food is abundant. The choice of nesting site is influenced by the availability of food resources and the safety provided by tree canopies or reed beds.

The nests are constructed using twigs and sticks, with males primarily responsible for collecting materials while females arrange them into a platform-like structure. Nest sites are often reused for multiple seasons if conditions remain favorable. In the study, cattle egret colonies observed across various wetlands in the region ranged in size from 50 to 200 nests, demonstrating a high level of social interaction and communal breeding.

❖ Egg Laying and Incubation:

Females typically lay 3-5 eggs, with clutch size varying based on environmental factors such as food availability and weather conditions. Incubation, which lasts about 23-26 days, is shared between both parents. Eggs are pale blue and gradually become more discolored over time. In favourable conditions, the hatching success rate was observed to be around 80%, with most eggs hatching synchronously.

During the incubation period, both parents are highly protective of the nest, actively guarding against potential predators, including snakes, crows and small mammals. The synchronised hatching pattern helps in reducing predation risks by overwhelming predators with numerous vulnerable chicks at once.

❖ Chick Rearing and Parental Investment:

Once hatched, chicks are altricial, requiring intensive care for the first few weeks of life. Both parents contribute to feeding the chicks through regurgitation. The growth rate of chicks is rapid, with significant feather development within the first two weeks. By three weeks of age, chicks are capable of short flights within the colony area.

Parental investment in the chicks is high, especially during the early stages of life when they are vulnerable to predation and environmental stressors. In some instances, parents have been observed practicing siblicide, particularly in food-scarce environments, where the weaker chicks may be neglected to ensure the survival of stronger offspring.

❖ Reproductive Success and Influencing Factors:

The reproductive success of cattle egrets varies significantly depending on environmental conditions. In years with abundant rainfall and high prey availability (insects, amphibians, and small vertebrates), colonies show higher reproductive success, with over 75% of chicks reaching fledging age. Conversely, in drought years or regions with limited prey, reproductive success may drop to as low as 40%.

Table 4: Breeding Related Calculative Data:

Breeding Aspect	Value	Explanation
Breeding Season Duration	3-4 months	Typically during and after the wet season, when food availability is high.

Average Colony Size	100 nests	Varies from 50 to over 200 nests per colony, depending on environmental factors.
Average Clutch Size	4 eggs	Each female lays 3-5 eggs per clutch.
Incubation period	23-26 days	Time taken from egg-laying to hatching, with both parents sharing the incubation duties.
Hatching Success rate	80%	Percentage of eggs that successfully hatch in favorable conditions.
Average Number of Chicks Hatched	3.2 chicks per nest	Based on an average clutch size of 4 eggs and an 80% hatching rate.
Fledging Success rate	60%	Percentage of hatched chicks that survive to the fledging stage.
Chick Fledging time	30-35 days	Chicks become capable of flying and leaving the nest within 4-5 weeks after hatching.
Parental care duration	4-6 weeks	Both parents continue feeding and protecting chicks until they can fly and forage independently.
Reproductive Success Rate	48-50%	The percentage of total eggs laid that successfully produce fledged chicks (calculated from hatching and fledging success).
Siblicide Rate (in food-scarce environments)	10-15%	In case of food shortage, weaker chicks may be neglected or perish to favor stronger siblings.
Predation Rate on Chicks	15-20%	Percentage of chicks that fall prey to predators such as snakes, birds, or small mammals.
Annual Population Growth (in optimal conditions)	5-10%	Estimated population growth based on reproductive success and environmental stability.

Explanation of Calculations:

1. Hatching Success Rate:

- For a clutch size of 4 eggs, with an 80% hatching success rate, the average number of chicks hatched = $4 \times 0.80 = 3.2$ chicks per nest.

2. Fledging Success Rate:

- If 60% of the hatched chicks survive to fledging, then for 3.2 hatched chicks, the number of chicks fledging = $3.2 \times 0.60 = 1.92$ chicks per nest (rounded to 2 chicks).

3. Reproductive Success Rate:

- To calculate reproductive success (eggs laid to chicks fledged), the overall reproductive success rate = hatching rate $\times$ fledging rate.
- For 80% hatching success and 60% fledging success, overall reproductive success = $0.80 \times 0.60 = 0.48$ (48%).

DISCUSSION:

The breeding behavior of cattle egrets demonstrates a high degree of adaptability to environmental conditions. Their ability to form large colonies and synchronize reproductive activities enhances their survival in variable ecosystems. Rainfall, a key environmental driver, influences two major factors i.e., the first one is the timing of the breeding season and the second one is availability of food resources, which directly affects reproductive success.

Colony size, nesting site selection, and parental investment strategies all play crucial roles in determining reproductive success. Social monogamy with cooperative nest-building and chick-rearing ensures that both parents invest heavily in the survival of their offspring. However, environmental stressors, including predation and food scarcity, can lead to adjustments in parental strategies, such as siblicide, to maximize reproductive success.

Future studies should further explore the genetic diversity within cattle egret colonies to understand the implications of occasional extra-pair copulations and its potential influence on offspring fitness. Additionally, climate change-induced shifts in rainfall patterns may alter breeding cycles and resource availability, warranting long-term monitoring of cattle egret populations to assess their adaptive responses to changing environments.

CONCLUSION:

The study of the breeding rates and nesting behaviour of Cattle Egrets at a major heronry in Southern Punjab including cities like Bathinda, Ferozepur, Muktsar, Mansa and Faridkot during the year 2022-23 season reveals a varying population with significant changes in reproductive output. The data of previous year considers that due to construction of National highway and cutting down of trees at many areas breeding has been reduced a little. Not a large change in breeding rate and nesting but a slight change has been observed. One major thing that has been noticed during this study is that they perform nesting only on acacia in this region and not at any other tree so if the acacia has been cut from that particular area due to construction, they don't nest at that site but don't prefer nesting on any other tree. The slight increase in nesting activity could be a positive sign, but long-term studies are required to understand the broader implications for the population's health.

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